

SOME EXAMPLES OF LACUNARY SEQUENCE SPACES ASSOCIATED WITH ORLICZ FUNCTION

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Abstract

This paper deals with the concepts of Lacunary sequence space, Orlicz function and Orlicz function spaces. Further we will study Lacunary sequence space associated with Orlicz functions together with investigation of some examples of Orlicz-Lacunary sequence space. We will also discuss 2-normed spaces and n -normed spaces with multi-sequences and show their involvement in examples of Lacunary-Orlicz functions. We will also discuss about Musielak-Orlicz function.

Keywords: Banach space, Difference operator, Uncertainty space, s -Young function \emptyset .

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Introduction

Sequences expressed by $\langle x_n \rangle$ are obviously Real or Complex accordingly $x_n \in R$ or C ; have beautiful shapes and natures when introduced with some equipment viz. increasing, decreasing, non-negativity, positive, bounded, convergent etc. collections of sequences with such equipment forms some beautiful spaces and the concepts of metrics, norms, inner products, topologies, Lacunary and Orlicz decorates them and enhances several concepts and opens field of investigations. A Lacunary Sequence is an increasing sequence $\theta = \langle x_k \rangle$ of non-negative integers, initiated with the condition $x_0 = 0$ and satisfying

$$h_n = x_n - x_{n-1} \rightarrow \infty$$

when $n \rightarrow \infty$ and the interval defined by θ is $I_k =]x_{k-1}, x_k]$

(Dowari, P. J. et. al. 2021). In 1978, A R Freedman et. al. defined a Lacunary sequence space $N_x = \{ \langle t_r \rangle \in I_k : \sum_{i \in I_k} |t_i - L| \rightarrow 0 \}$ by defining strongly Cesaro-summable sequences $[\sum_{i=x_{k-1}+1}^{x_k} |t_i - L| = \sum_{i \in I_k} |t_i - L|]$ in respect to a Lacunary ‘strongly convergent’ sequence $x = \langle x_k \rangle$ (Ayhan ESI, 2012; Aiyub, M., 2014 & Raj, K. et. al. 2023). Gähler, in 1963 introduced the notion of dual-metric and consequently, in 1965 he evolved the 2-normed concept (Ö. KİŞİ, and M. GÜRDAL, 2022) and further this concept were improved and generalized to n -normed by several Mathematician. Pringsheim (1897), Hardy (1904), Bromwich (1908), Moricz (1979), Basarir (1999), Zeltser (2001), Das & Tripathy (2020) and others have worked on the development of multi-sequences viz their convergence, divergence and some other properties. (Kavyasree, P. R. and Reddy, B. S., 2018; Ö. KİŞİ, and M. GÜRDAL, 2022). Initiation of Orlicz spaces were carried by Z. W. Birnbaum and W. Orlicz in 1931 by the generalization of Lebesgue spaces (Kustiawan, C et. al. 2023) while the detail study of Orlicz functions were discussed by J. LINDENSTRAUSS AND L. TZAFRIRI (1970) and they have also discussed the involvement of M. A. Krasnoselskii and Ya. B. Rutickii (1961) and . K. J. Lindberg (1970) in the development of Orlicz functions and spaces.

Definition-1 Orlicz function: An Orlicz function O is defined as a function on non-negative real numbers (i.e. $[0, \infty[$) such that O is

1. continuous
2. non-decreasing
3. convex with the following two more conditions
4. $O(0) = 0$, $O(x) > 0$ for $x > 0$ and
5. $O(x) \rightarrow \infty$ as $x \rightarrow \infty$. (M. Aiyub, 2014. AYHAN ESI, 2012) .

Definition-2 Orlicz function space: the Orlicz sequence space, a generalization of Banach Space, defined as the sequence space l_O associated with Orlicz function O with the condition (J. LINDENSTRAUSS AND L. TZAFRIRI, 1971)

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} O\left(|x_n|/t\right) < \infty; t > 0 \text{ and } x = \langle x_n \rangle \in l_O \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

With the defining norm on l_O

$$\| \langle x_n \rangle \| = \inf \left\{ t > 0; \sum_1^{\infty} O\left(|x_n|/t\right) \leq 1 \right\} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Kustiawan, C. et. al. (2023) have discussed s -Young function \emptyset , defined on $[0, \infty)$ which is continuous, s -convex and satisfying the following two conditions

- (i) $\emptyset(0) = 0$, and
- (ii) $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \emptyset(x) = \infty$.

With this s -Young function \emptyset , they have represented Orlicz sequence space, with the above conditions (1) and (2) when replacing Orlicz function O by the s -Young function \emptyset .

Definition-3 2-normed space: On a vector space $X(R)$ ($\dim \geq 2$), 2-norm denoted by $\|.,.\|$ is a real valued function on $X \times X$, satisfying below conditions,

- (i) $\|x_i, x_j\| \geq 0$
- (ii) $\|x_i, x_j\| = 0$ iff x_i & x_j are linearly dependent.
- (iii) $\|x_i, x_j\| = \|x_j, x_i\|$.
- (iv) $\|\mu x_i, x_j\| = |\mu| \|x_i, x_j\|$, for every $\mu \in R$.
- (v) $\|\alpha_i + \beta_i, x_j\| \leq \|\alpha_i, x_j\| + \|\beta_i, x_j\|$

for $x_i, x_j, \alpha_i, \beta_i \in X$. Vector space X , paired with 2-norm, is named as 2-normed space. A simple example of 2-norm $\|\cdot, \cdot\|$ on a vector space X can be defined as

$$\|x_i, x_j\| = \left| \det. \begin{bmatrix} x_i & x_j \\ \bar{x}_j & \bar{x}_i \end{bmatrix} \right|$$

Definition-4 n -normed space: On a vector space $X(R)$ ($Dim. \geq n$), an n -norm, symbolled by $\|\cdot, \cdot, \dots, \cdot\|_X$, being a real valued map on X^n , satisfy the following five criterion (Kavyasree, P. R. and Reddy, B. S., **2018**, Ö. KİŞİ, and M. GÜRDAL, **2022**, Sharma, S.K. and Ayhan Asi **2014**)

1. $\|x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\| \geq 0$
2. $\|x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\| = 0$ if and only if all the co-ordinates $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ are linearly dependent.
3. The value $\|x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\|$ remains invariant whatever be the position of co-ordinates $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$.
4. $\|\mu x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\| = |\mu| \|x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\|$ for any scalar μ .
5. $\|\alpha_1 + \beta_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\| \leq \|\alpha_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\| + \|\beta_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n\|$

For $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n, \alpha_1, \beta_1 \in X$. The vector space X when equipped with an n -norm is termed by n -normed space.

Definition-5 Double Lacunary sequence: A sequence $\{t_{i,j} : i, j \in N\}$ of double array (called double sequence) such that $\{t_{i,j} : i, j \in N\} = \{k_i, l_j\}$, where both the sequences k_i & l_j are increasing with nonnegative integral numbers having initial conditions $k_0 = l_0 = 0$, is called a Lacunary sequence if satisfy

- (i) $h_i = k_i - k_{i-1} \rightarrow \infty$ when $i \rightarrow \infty$ and
- (ii) $\bar{h}_j = l_j - l_{j-1} \rightarrow \infty$ when $j \rightarrow \infty$

(1) Ayhan ASI (2012) defined an ideal on a non-empty set X , and taken an ideal I_2 on the

set $2^{N \times N}$ further assumed $\omega(n - X)$ as X -valued sequence space. $\omega_{\{t_{i,j}\}}^{I_2}[O, \alpha, \|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|_X]$ is an example of Orlicz-Lacunary sequence which combines Orlicz function O and double Lacunary sequence $\{t_{i,j} : i, j \in N\} = \{t_{i,j}\}$,

which is given as

$$\omega_{\{t_{i,j}\}}^{I_2}[O, \alpha, \|\cdot, \dots, \cdot\|_X] = \{ \langle x_{k,l} \rangle \in \omega(n - X) : \left((i, j) \in I_{i,j} : \frac{1}{h_{i,j}} \sum_{(k,l) \in I_{i,j}} \left[O \left(\left\| \left(\frac{x_{k,l} - L}{\rho}, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n \right) \right\| \right) \right]^{\alpha_{k,l}} \geq \varepsilon \right) \in I_2 ; \forall \varepsilon > 0, \text{ for some positive } \rho \text{ \& for } y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n \in X \}$$

The symbols have following meaning

(i) $h_{i,j} = h_i \cdot \bar{h}_j$

(ii) $I_{i,j} = \{(k, l) : k_{i-1} \leq k \leq k_i \text{ and } l_{j-1} \leq l \leq l_j\}$

(iii) $\alpha = \langle \alpha_{k,l} \rangle$ be a strictly increasing and positive real-valued sequence.

(2) Mohammad Aiyub (2014) defined the sequence of Orlicz functions O_t which was called

Musiellak-Orlicz function, denoted by $M = \langle O_t \rangle$. For $n=2$, $\omega(2 - X)$ as X -valued function, $[\omega^\theta, M, \alpha, a, s, \|\cdot, \cdot\|]_\delta^\infty(\Delta_Z^m)$ is an example of Orlicz-Lacunary sequence space which is a combination of Musiellak-Orlicz function M and Lacunary sequence θ , defined as $[\omega^\theta, M, \alpha, a, s, \|\cdot, \cdot\|]_\delta^\infty(\Delta_Z^m) = \{x = \langle x_i \rangle \in \omega(2 - X) :$

$$\sup_{r,n} \frac{1}{h_r} \sum_{k \in I_r} \left(\frac{1}{k}\right)^s a_k \left[M_k \left(\left\| \frac{t_{kn}(\Delta_Z^m x_k)}{\rho}, z \right\| \right) \right]^{\alpha_k} < \infty; \text{ for } \rho > 0, \& s \geq 0 \}$$

The symbols have the following meaning

- (i) $\alpha = \langle \alpha_k \rangle$ is a strictly increasing positive real-valued sequence.
(ii) $a = \langle a_k \rangle$ is a sequence of non-zero real numbers.
(iii) Δ_z^m stands for difference operator given by

$$\Delta_z^m x_k = \Delta_z^{m-1} x_k - \Delta_z^{m-1} x_{k-1}$$

and in a generalization form, it is defined by the formula

$$\Delta_z^m x_k = \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{m}{i} z_{k+i} x_{k+i}; \forall k \in N$$

- (iv) σ is a mapping on the set of positive integers and thereafter t_{kn} is given as

$$t_{kn}(x_k) = \frac{(x_{\sigma^1(n)} + x_{\sigma^2(n)} + x_{\sigma^3(n)} + \cdots + x_{\sigma^k(n)}) + x_n}{k+1}$$

- (3) Let $\mathcal{U} = (\mathcal{T}, \mathcal{L}, \mathcal{M})$ be an uncertainty space defined in Dowari, P. J. & Tripathy, B. C.

(2021), for a non-empty set \mathcal{L} whose members are called event, \mathcal{T} is a σ -algebra defined on \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{M} be a set function which is after satisfying four axioms known as an uncertain measure. Now, assuming the classes of uncertain sequences in \mathcal{U} given as

$$[U_\theta, O]_0 = \left\{ \omega = \langle \omega_n \rangle \right. \\ \left. : \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} O \left(\frac{\|\omega_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho} \right) = 0 ; \text{for } \langle \omega_n \rangle \in \mathcal{U} \text{ \& some } \rho > 0 \right\},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
[U_\theta, O]_\infty &= \left\{ \omega = \langle \omega_n \rangle \right. \\
&: \left. \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho}\right) < \infty ; \text{for } \langle \omega_n \rangle \in \mathcal{U} \text{ \& some } \rho > 0 \right\} \& \\
[U_\theta, O]_1 &= \left\{ \omega = \langle \omega_n \rangle \right. \\
&: \left. \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega_n(\gamma) - L(\gamma)\|}{\rho}\right) = 0 ; \text{for } \langle \omega_n \rangle \in \mathcal{U}, \text{ some } \right. \\
&\quad \left. \rho > 0 \text{ and } L(\gamma) \in \mathcal{U} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

All the three classes $[U_\theta, O]_0, [U_\theta, O]_\infty$ & $[U_\theta, O]_1$ are linear spaces. We claim one among them (taking $[U_\theta, O]_\infty$) and follow the similar.

$[U_\theta, O]_\infty$ is a vector space:

Let $\omega'_n, \omega''_n \in [U_\theta, O]_\infty$, then for $\rho_1, \rho_2 > 0$ we have

$$\sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_1}\right) < \infty \ \& \ \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_2}\right) < \infty$$

Assuming $\rho_3 = \max\{2|x|\rho_1, 2|y|\rho_2\}$, where $x, y \in \mathbb{C}$ then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|x\omega'_n(\gamma) + y\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_3}\right) &\leq \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|x\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_3} + \frac{\|y\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_3}\right) \\
&\leq \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{|x|\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_3}\right) + \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{|y|\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_3}\right) \\
&\leq \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{2\rho_1}\right) + \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{2\rho_2}\right) \\
&\leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_1}\right) + \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_2}\right) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$< \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_1}\right) + \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_2}\right) < \infty$$

i.e. we have $x\omega'_n(\gamma) + y\omega''_n(\gamma) \in [U_\theta, O]_\infty$ implies that $[U_\theta, O]_\infty$ is a vector space. Further,

$[U_\theta, O]_\infty$ Is a normed linear space:

Defining the norm on $[U_\theta, O]_\infty$ given by

$$\|\omega\| = \inf. \left\{ \rho > 0 \right.$$

$$\left. : \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega_n\|}{\rho}\right) \leq 1 ; \text{for } \omega = \langle \omega_n \rangle \in \mathcal{U} \text{ \&for every } k \right.$$

$$\left. \in N \right\}$$

Now, choosing $\rho_1 > 0, \rho_2 > 0$ such that

$$\sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_1}\right) \leq 1 \text{ \& } \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_2}\right) \leq 1$$

Assuming $\rho_1 + \rho_2 = \rho$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma) + \omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho}\right) \\ & \leq \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma) + \omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_1 + \rho_2}\right) \\ & \leq \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\rho_1}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} \frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_1} + \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} \frac{\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_2}\right) \\ & \leq \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega'_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_1}\right) + \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} o\left(\frac{\|\omega''_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho_2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{\rho_1}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} + \frac{\rho_2}{\rho_1 + \rho_2} \\ \leq 1$$

Which immediately result that

$$\|\omega\| = \|\omega' + \omega''\| = \|\omega'\| + \|\omega''\|, \text{ where } \omega = \omega' + \omega''$$

Also, for non-zero $\mu \in \mathbb{C}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mu\omega\| &= \|\mu \cdot \omega_n\| \\ &= \inf. \left\{ \rho > 0 \right. \\ &\quad \left. : \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} O\left(\frac{\|\mu\omega_n(\gamma)\|}{\rho}\right) \leq 1 ; \text{ for every } k \in N \right\} \\ &= \inf. \left\{ r > 0 : \sup_k \frac{1}{h_k} \sum_{n \in I_k} O\left(\frac{\|\omega_n\|}{r}\right) \leq 1 ; \text{ for every } k \in N \& r = \frac{\rho}{|\mu|} \right\} \\ &= |\mu| \|\omega_n\| \end{aligned}$$

Hence the proof

This space $[U_\theta, O]_\infty$ is a combination of lacunary sequence θ and Orlicz function O , hence is an example of Orlicz-Lacunary sequence space.

Conclusion

(1), (2) and (3) are the three examples of Orlicz-Lacunary sequence space.

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